

Unpacking Participatory Research in a Cross-Sectoral Transitions to School Project

Joni Clarke

joni.clarke58@mail.dcu.ie

This paper problematises the challenges experienced in enacting participatory research in the current PhD study. The study sought to address outcomes in mathematics for Irish children from socioeconomically disadvantaged contexts, and the pedagogical discontinuity across the preschool to primary school transition that is seen to compound the issue. While participatory research methods have grown in prominence across a number of fields as a way to actively involve community members as co-researchers, it has not been widely used in the context of Irish education. Two case study settings were involved, each bringing together preschool and primary school teachers to create cross-sectoral learning communities. However, the challenges faced in realising participation in the research process resulted in the need for a methodological pivot in the second cycle. The focus of participation shifted from co-researching to participation in ‘communicative spaces’ that provide a forum for teachers’ practice, understanding and knowledge to be collectively examined, resulting in actions that challenge ‘the way things are done around here’. Reflection on the factors that constrained participation as co-researchers pointed to structural, systemic, educator and researcher/design factors. Acknowledging ‘uncomfortable’ truths in relation to the research process highlighted several ethical considerations and facilitated an understanding of the conditions and processes that could enable different forms of meaningful participation in future research.

Keywords: Critical Participatory Action Research, Participatory Research Approaches, Ethics in Participatory Research, Cross Sectoral Professional Learning

Highlights

- The nature of the ‘participation’ of community members can vary in participatory research however, the collaboration between academic researcher and community members must privilege the agendas and perspectives of the co-researchers
- Research design and researcher expectations must be cognisant that the participation of community members as co-researchers is not a given
- In Ireland, structural and systemic factors impede meaningful, sustained, collaborative PD experiences

Introduction

Engaged research approaches share a common interest in advancing interests of social concern ‘with’ social partners rather than ‘for’ them (Irish Universities Association, 2022). The focus on applied research that engages directly with impacted communities and contributes to social change aligns with global trends towards ‘the engaged university’ (Watson, 2011). In my own institution, Dublin City University (DCU), The Centre for Engaged Research (2023, p.2) state that ‘active engagement with society such as with community organisations or marginalised groups can offer indispensable knowledge and in turn play a key role in policy-making and addressing social issues’. Under this umbrella, participatory action research (PAR) has garnered much attention across numerous fields as a methodology that seeks to move beyond conventional research methods, which have often overlooked community needs and perspectives (Singh, 2018). Instead, in PAR, community co-researchers are typically involved in all stages of research cycles; from identifying the research question, research design, implementing action, collecting and analysing data and disseminating results on topics that impact them.

Many authors have considered the forms and quality of participation that constitutes ‘genuine’ or ‘meaningful’ PAR, outlining a hierarchy; from ‘deeper’ levels of participation (Arnstein, 1969) where all processes are under full community control (Banks et al., 2013). Here, co-researchers have equal status and partner on research grants and programs, co-steer the questions and direction of research, interpret data and act on implications of these together (Oliver et al., 2019), and share power and control in decision making (Arnstein, 1969). In contrast, minimal levels or ‘tokenistic’ participation (Arnstein, 1969) are characterised by processes which are mainly controlled by the academic researcher with only some community input (Banks et al., 2013), or ‘shallow-level’ involvement where the research findings are simply shared with participants (Oliver et al., 2019).

While there is some consensus on the types of processes and activities that constitute ‘deeper’ forms of participation, it is acknowledged that it is often difficult to attain in practice (Blumenthal, 2011). For example, time parameters within the academic researcher’s setting or the school setting may constrain participation, as can the various levels of expertise. For example, Hanson (2001) explains, written publications and in-depth data analysis may be better suited to academic researcher’s skill set. Acknowledging the reality of pre-existing skill sets, Kwan and Walsh (2018) add that a rigid focus on equal participation and failure to

acknowledge prior inequalities can ultimately cause harm to co-researchers. Therefore, participation need not occur at all aspects of the research process in equal amounts (Hansen et al., 2001), and context and circumstance help to determine the type of participation that is meaningful.

Expanding on previous definitions of ‘participation’, Kemmis et al., (2014) contend that the key imperative of participation in Critical PAR (CPAR) is participation in a public sphere and participation with others in communicative action (Habermas, 1981). This entails conversation in which people strive for intersubjective agreement about the ideas and the language they use, mutual understanding of one another’s perspectives and points of view, and unforced consensus about what to do, emphasising improvement in the lives and settings of the research participants (Kemmis et al., 2014). While there are various views of what constitutes participation, most agree that PR must privilege the agendas and perspectives of the co-researchers (Lenette, 2022) and be responsive to their views, aspirations and needs (Arnstein, 1969),

Importantly, PAR is not only an approach to research, but also a form of professional development (PD) that can lead to teacher professional learning (Tok et al., 2024). Specifically, it is a form of PD that foregrounds teachers experience, is context specific (Feekery, 2023) and site-ontological (Kemmis et al., 2014). This is relevant given that school improvement research suggests that for PD to be worthwhile, it must be tailored to the situated realities and contexts of the given school (Murphy, 2020). Often, attempts at school reform ‘ignore the contents of what economists called the ‘black box’ of local practices, beliefs, and traditions’ (McLaughlin, 1990, p.11) resulting in little change.

Methods

The present study brought together early years educators (EYE) and primary school infant teachers in cross-sectoral professional learning communities. This created a space where both sectors could work to address the pedagogical discontinuities in mathematics which are known to contribute to the poor outcomes often experienced by children in disadvantaged contexts. National assessments of mathematics (NAMER’21) highlight the problem, revealing that 48.6% of sixth class children in Urban DEIS 1 schools scored at the lowest two levels, Level 1 and Below Level 1 of the five proficiency levels used in the assessment. Given that almost two decades of the DEIS initiative has not resulted in

improvements in mathematics outcomes in Urban DEIS 1 schools (Nelis and Gilleece, 2023), new approaches and greater attention to the issue are needed.

An outline of the research study was emailed to Urban DEIS 1 schools inviting expressions of interest. Schools were chosen based on their ability to secure commitment from preschool partners; ensure that the majority of the preschool's children would transfer to their primary school; and commit to finding time where both groups could meet weekly. Site one consisted of four EYE and six primary teachers, site two consisted of six EYE and six primary teachers (including one home school community liaison teacher). Ethical approval from the author's research ethics committee was given to engage with EYE and teachers as co-researchers. In addition to written information about the project, face to face meetings with the educators were held in order to fully explain the implications of their involvement as co-researchers. Group norms were used to establish that all members were of equal status within the group, that the practices and traditions of each sector were to be valued and respected, and that the expertise held by each group member was to be foregrounded.

In response to the poor mathematical outcomes generally experienced by children in disadvantaged settings, this study took a critical social justice stance underpinned by the belief that education systems act to reproduce existing levels of educational advantage and disadvantage (Bourdieu and Passeron, 1990). It was fitting that the research methodology aligned in principle with the values underpinning this perspective; namely inclusion and participation. Therefore CPAR (Kemmis et al., 2014) was fitting as a research methodology but also as an approach to PD in that it satisfied the three essential considerations central to sustainable school change: consideration of external contexts, internal contexts, and change processes (Murphy, 2020). Furthermore, given that the literature on educational research in Ireland revealed little evidence of PAR and no use of CPAR, it was an opportunity to explore the factors that supported or constrained this approach.

Findings

In this contribution I wish to problematise aspects of the 'participatory' process - as ultimately participation in the 'research' process did not eventuate. While initially the cross-sectoral group members in both sites were enthusiastic, built relationships, and visited each other's settings to gain an understanding of respective practices, ultimately the next steps in identifying a research question and project was met with resistance and discomfort. While

there was interest in improving teaching and learning in early mathematics and in improving transitions practices, there was simply little interest in becoming involved in a research process. In short, it seemed the teachers in both the preschool and primary school settings wanted to engage in PD but not in research. After reflection based upon semi-structured interviews and researcher reflective diaries, the factors that constrained participation as co-researchers were broadly categorised as: structural, systemic, educator and researcher/design related.

Structural Factors

Structural barriers to participation included time, and while not unique to PR, the cross-curricular nature of this study complicated logistical arrangements regarding meeting times and places. In the Irish context, little time for PD is structurally embedded into the educator's workload. Additionally, extended PD time frames are important in research that relies on relational quality and trust, particularly when working cross-sectorally. Given the recent policy push toward greater collaboration between ECEC and primary sectors to facilitate continuity in school transitions (e.g. see First 5 2019; Aistear 2024; Primary Curriculum Framework 2023; Wellbeing Policy Statement and Framework for Practice 2018/2019; DEIS Plan 2017), this must be viewed as a basic prerequisite. Both settings worked hard to find meeting times that were least disruptive to children's learning. The EYE commitment was evident in them choosing to give up part of their lunch break in order to take part in the project, exemplifying how lack of structural support, contributes to a PD system in Ireland that relies heavily on 'goodwill' (Moloney, 2011, p.11). Progress was compounded by the teacher shortages being faced by both sectors as 'cover' to attend meetings was often difficult to find when staff were spread thinly covering sick colleagues or dealing with unexpected incidents involving children and parents. Additionally, the short-term nature of many contracts, that feeds into teacher transience, added to the impact felt by high staff-turnover. Staff turnover and unavailability impacted the cohesiveness of the group and the progress that could be made as experience, momentum and knowledge was routinely lost. The issue of participant turn-over in this study is emblematic of a larger concern regarding the impact of short-term contracts, staff-shortages and high turnover (particularly in more challenging DEIS contexts and because of poor working conditions in the ECEC sector) on schools' ability to focus on the task of teaching and learning and to engage in collaborative professional learning opportunities that are impactful and sustainable, an issue that warrants further research.

Systemic Factors

In relation to systemic factors, the cross-sectoral and participatory nature of the project challenged existing PD cultures where ‘delivery of content’ and individual PD was the norm in both settings. Participant confidence and experience in collaborative problem solving processes played some part in the difficulties experienced when trying to identify research questions. It also became clear that cross-sectoral collaboration required significant relationship-building between two sectors that hold two very different professional status’ and often education status’. Here, the communicative space provided a forum to examine and understand the ‘others’ practices, cultures, languages, histories and philosophies.

Educator Factors

Teacher-level factors relating to participation in the research process included confidence, career stage and existing levels of pedagogical and content knowledge (although, these might also be conceived of as structural and systemic factors.) Teachers who were coming towards the end of their careers showed less interest in engaging in research and in the project suggesting an ‘I know this already’ attitude, while some early-career teachers were contending with emotional exhaustion from having ‘troubled’ and ‘violent’ children in their junior infant classrooms, children characterised as ‘not being able to cope in the new setting’. These children and the lack of support available to them (where provision of AIM workers in the preschool setting does not automatically transfer to an SNA in the school setting), impacted the teacher’s capacity for PD and teaching and learning matters. However, although in a ‘finding their feet’ phase, early-career teachers reported that establishing ‘good practices’ early on was important and helpful to them.

A seminal learning from this first cycle was that it was difficult for educators to engage confidently in participatory research without first addressing their pedagogical content knowledge (Shulman, 1986). For example, initially the primary teachers wanted to learn from the play-based practices that they assumed were used in the preschool setting in order to support their implementation of the new Primary mathematics curriculum. However it became apparent that both settings needed support in the playful approaches espoused in their respective curricula as existing practices did not reflect the intend curriculum in either setting. As a result the next cycle involved a series of workshops that built a common knowledge base, shared understandings and shared language which then positioned the cross-sectoral group to devise a shared early maths transitions project.

Academic Researcher and Design Factors

Given its commitment to democratising research and to social change, it has been argued that participatory research re-positions our understanding of research ethics within the broader socio-political, global context of our everyday lives (Cahill, 2015). In this way, the values, moral and ethical stance of the researcher and co-researchers play a role in framing the research. In the present study a social justice stance was held in regard to the impact that poorer mathematical outcomes have on some children's ability to access, participate, engage, and benefit from education. However, while this was the stance held by the academic researcher, it was not necessarily the viewpoint held by participants. In this way, the imposition of one's own ethical viewpoint on the group, was problematic. As researchers undertaking interpretative or qualitative research often discover, methodological and ethical issues are often 'inextricably interwoven' (Cohen, Manion, and Morrisson, 2011, p.89). However, the creation of a communicative space enabled different viewpoints to be discussed, revealing that group members had other reasons for improving children's mathematics including: teachers' own professional learning, teachers' improved sense of agency, a children's learning perspective- where being good at maths was seen as a positive end in itself, and lastly, as a vehicle for improving transitions practices. As Kemmis et al. (2014, p. 5) explain, 'the commitment to communicative action opens up communicative space so that the disciplined work of CPAR can occur, building solidarity and underwriting understandings and decisions with legitimacy and validity'.

As all participants had been well informed as to the participatory nature of the study at its outset via information sheets and information meetings, the reluctance in engaging in the research aspect of the study, highlighted that well informed consent in research does not guarantee participant engagement, enthusiasm or conviction. In this way the recruitment process in participatory research becomes central in ensuring a truly participatory process. Recruiting via a gate-keeper such as a school principal or ECEC leader poses conflicts for staff who do not wish to participate and ethical implications for the researcher. In future, it would be preferable to recruit in ways that target educators directly.

In contrast to much of the literature on PAR, in this study, the community partners were presented with a specific topic, 'continuity in early mathematics' within which to conduct a research study. Here the research fell into one of the traps of pseudo democracy and pseudo participation described by Hanson et al. (2001, p.318) where, 'the academic research agenda can define the issues to be researched from the outset'. Ensuring that the

research topic is defined by community members feeds into their motivation as well as the democratic process that CPAR espouses.

Of further concern is the complex role of the academic as researcher, co-participant, and knowledgeable other which can present challenges and raises potential risks to ethical conduct. It was difficult to define my role and I questioned the authenticity of my role as participant. While it has been said that PAR democratises research by challenging the idea of who can be the expert (e.g. Lenette, 2022), and should foreground the lived experiences and tacit knowledge of co-researchers, it is acknowledged that there is a need for a knowledgeable other in professional development (Darling-Hammond et al., 2017). However, the risk-minimisation strategies of Groundwater-Smith and Kemmis (2004) were useful, including: possessing an established record of working with schools; building clear, shared understandings of goals, roles and expectations; establishing relationships based on mutual trust, recognition, and respect; and exploring the strengths and needs for expertise each participant brings to the relationship. Over time, these strategies served to minimise inherent power differentials.

Discussion

Boyle et al., (2022, p. 909) outline that as the popularity of AR grows in education, its reporting has become more ‘technically orientated and instrumental and typically framed only as it relates to the ‘good news’ stories of success’. Considering this and resisting the temptation of skipping over unexpected and unwanted results in favour of ‘valorising accounts of success’ (Boyle et al., 2022, p. 909) it was important to share the messiness and difficulties that were part of the present research process. Being committed to practitioner reflection, this must include what Pillow (2003) describes as a ‘reflexivity of discomfort’. It was important to add to the discourse on how difficult change in education is to achieve. It is hoped that reporting of ‘uncomfortable truths’ where unintended out-comes, including failure, discomfort, tension, and challenges are presented (Boyle et al. 2022) in the hope of providing insights into the processes involved in professional development in schools and in particular the challenges of participatory approaches. Boyle et al., (2022, p. 910) outline that given the ‘favoured emancipatory’ nature of critical action research it is particularly important to provide truthful and nuanced accounts that provide authentic representations of

change in schools. Not only is reporting uncomfortable truths, ethically appropriate but also ‘can act as points of reference for change’ (Kemmis et al., 2014, p. 274).

Conclusion

Given the rapid pace of educational change in Ireland and the curriculum overload reported by primary teachers (Martinez-Sainz et al., 2023), it is important to explore approaches to PD and policy implementation that offer ways for schools to make sense of changes in their own terms, that are specific to their unique contexts and cultures. The present research suggests that PAR could be helpful in achieving this, if the level of participation is determined by the interests and needs of the group rather than those of the academic researcher. In the present study, while participation as co-researchers did not eventuate in cycle one, subsequent cycles saw participation in planning and steering the PD content including coaching sessions, participation in communicative action and participation in devising collaborative, cross sectoral projects. Furthermore, CPAR has good suitability to working cross-sectorally: the reframing of practices from a cross-sectoral perspective served to position the child at the centre of the group’s decision-making process rather than their respective institutional norms. Finally, the academic researcher’s desire to ‘democratise’ the research process cannot be an end in itself, rather the ethical imperative for the process of participation must be set in terms that are of real benefit to the community group and those they impact- in doing so it should be acknowledged that being engaged in a ‘research’ process might not be of benefit to the needs of the group or simply, not of interest to them. In a truly democratic process, the level and type of participation, for example, participation in the research process or participation in sustained collective investigation within a communicative space (Kemmis et al., 2014) should be determined in collaboration with the group.

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